

Ocean water quality monitoring using remote sensing techniques: a review

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ABSTRACT

Ocean Water Quality (OWQ) monitoring provides insights into the quality of water in marine and near-shore environments. OWQ measurements can contain the physical, chemical, and biological characteristics of oceanic waters, where low OWQ values indicate an unhealthy ecosystem. Many parameters of water can be estimated from Remote Sensing (RS) data. Thus, RS offers significant opportunities for monitoring water quality in estuaries, coastal waterways, and the ocean. This paper reviews various RS systems and techniques for OWQ monitoring. It first introduces the common OWQ parameters, followed by the definition of the parameters and techniques of OWQ monitoring with RS techniques. In this study, the following OWQ parameters were reviewed: chlorophyll-a, colored dissolved organic matter, turbidity or total suspended matter/solid, dissolved organic carbon, Secchi disk depth, suspended sediment concentration, and sea surface temperature. This study presents a systematic analysis of the capabilities and types of spaceborne systems (e.g., optical and thermal sensors, passive microwave radiometers, active microwave scatterometers, and altimeters) which are commonly applied to OWQ assessment. The paper also provides a summary of the opportunities and limitations of RS data for spatial and temporal estimation of OWQ. Overall, it was observed that chlorophyll-a and colored dissolved organic matter are the dominant parameters applied to OWQ monitoring. It was also concluded that the data from optical and passive microwave sensors could effectively be applied to estimate OWQ parameters. From a methodological perspective, semi-empirical algorithms generally outperform the other empirical, analytical, and semi-analytical methods for OWQ monitoring.

Keywords: water quality; oceans; remote sensing.

31 **1. Introduction**

32 According to the definitions of the environmental protection agencies, such as the United States
33 (US) Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), Food and Drug Administration (FDA), and World
34 Health Organization (WHO), Water Quality (WQ) generally refers to the physical, chemical, and
35 biological characteristics of water. WQ determines water suitability for different applications, such
36 as recreation, drinking, fishing, agriculture, and industry (Chapelle, Bradley et al. 2009). Ocean
37 Water Quality (OWQ) assessment is crucial because nearly 97% of Earth's water and 90% of its
38 biosphere are found in the ocean (Alizadeh and Kavianpour 2015). Moreover, the importance of
39 OWQ in estuaries and coastal regions is undeniable because almost 40% of the world's population
40 lives in coastal regions, within 100 km of coastlines (Costanza 1999). Additionally, aquatic
41 vegetation in the ocean absorbs approximately 30% of the CO₂ emissions produced by humans
42 (Häder and Barnes 2019, Su, Cai et al. 2020) and generates 50–80% of the oxygen in the Earth's
43 atmosphere (NOAA 2017). The oceans are also home to millions of species of fish, marine
44 mammals (including herbivores, baleen whales, and top predators), and coral reefs (Ouma, Noor
45 et al. 2020). Thus, any uncontrolled changes in OWQ may endanger the habitats of millions of
46 aquatic organisms, public health, coastal environment, carbon cycle, ecosystem health, habitats of
47 underwater flora and fauna, economy, and overall health of the environment (Palmer, Bonilla et
48 al. 2008). In light of these factors, OWQ monitoring using advanced and accurate techniques is
49 essential for various purposes.

50 OWQ parameters can be divided into three categories: physical, biological, and chemical (Usali
51 and Ismail 2010). Physical properties include temperature, color, turbidity, and odor (Shifrin
52 1998). On the other hand, chemical characteristics are factors that influence the water molecule,
53 including pH, dissolved oxygen, as well as total solids and suspended solids (Akinde and Obire

54 2011). Biological category include the parameters that affect the availability of water as a solvent
 55 (McCain, Hooker et al. 2006). It should be noted that physical, biological, and chemical parameters
 56 can also affect each other. For example, the number of suspended particles impacts the color of
 57 water, and the temperature and Chlorophyll influence the amount of flora (Bussmann and Kattner
 58 2000). Overall, all the physical, biological, and chemical properties are important for OWQ
 59 analysis.

60 OWQ is measured by the number of particles within pure water. Pure water has some known and
 61 detectable properties that are affected by the presence of impurities in the water. Therefore, the
 62 study of the impurities that affect the physical, chemical, and biological properties of water is one
 63 of the most common approaches for estimating OWQ parameters. Table 1 shows some of the most
 64 common WQ parameters, their units, and their appropriate range for Ocean Water (OW) and other
 65 water bodies. It must be noted that the ranges mentioned in Table 1 are not fixed and may vary
 66 based on different applications, study area, geological properties of the water body, depth of
 67 sampling, and water temperature.

68 Table 1: The most common WQ parameters.

Physical /Chemical parameters	Unit	Ocean and other water bodies	Reference
Smell	–	Not Smell (Saltwater by itself)	(Peters and Steinberg 2019)
Flavor	–	Normal	(Spanton and Saputra 2017)
pH	–	6.5–8.5	(Parker 2016)
Chlorophyll-a	mg/m ³	0.01–20	(Sigman and Hain 2012)
Electrical Conductivity	µS/cm	~30,000–60,000	(Sauerheber and Heinz 2015)
Surface Temperature	°C	-2 to 36 °C (Average about 15 °C)	(Segar 1997)
Total Dissolved Solid	mg/l	>35,000	(Kim, Son et al. 2017)
Dissolved Organic Matter	µmol/ kg	30–100	(Hansell, Carlson et al. 2009)
Dissolved oxygen	mg/l	0–10	(Crust 1977)
Biochemical Oxygen Demand	mg/l	0–3	(Abdelmongy and El-Moselhy 2015)

Chemical Oxygen Demand	mg/l	0–8000	(Poblete-Chávez, Cortés-Pizarro et al. 2016)
Hardness	mg/l	0–1000	(Karim, Uddin et al. 2019)
Alkalinity	mMol /l	19–600	(Kucuik 2014)
Chloride	mg/l	0–250	(Spanton and Saputra 2017)
Salinity	ppm	10,000–35,000	(Alizadeh and Kavianpour 2015)
Phosphate-phosphorus	μmol	0–2	(Šupraha, Gerech et al. 2015)
Nitrate-nitrogen	μmol/kg	20–40	(Webb)
Nitrite-nitrogen	mg/l	<0.5	(Crosby, Hill et al. 2006)
Ammonia	mg/l	<2	(Crosby, Hill et al. 2006)
Total Suspended Solids	mg/l	0–50	(Nemeth and Nowlis 2001)
Turbidity or water clarity	NTU	10–30	(Luis, Rheuban et al. 2019)
Ocean Color	TCU	0–15	(Devlin, Petus et al. 2015)
Secchi Disk Depth	m	0-50	(Lee, Shang et al. 2016)

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70 Due to the variety of pollution sources that make their way into the ocean and affect OWQ, it is
71 difficult to provide a comprehensive list of qualitative OWQ parameters (Gholizadeh, Melesse et
72 al. 2016). However, the most common OWQ parameters are Chlorophyll-a (Chl-a), Sea Surface
73 Temperature (SST), turbidity, Sea Surface Salinity (SSS), Colored Dissolved Organic Matter
74 (CDOM), Ocean Color (OC), Secchi Disk Depth (SDD), Total Suspended Solids (TSS), Total
75 Phosphorus (TP), Suspended Sediment Concentration (SSC), Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Dissolved
76 Organic Carbon (DOC), electrical conductivity, nitrate, and sulfate (Hall, Zaffiro et al. 2007,
77 Sánchez, Colmenarejo et al. 2007). It is worth noting that some of these parameters are mutually
78 interrelated (Gholizadeh, Melesse et al. 2016).

79 There are generally three approaches for measuring and monitoring OWQ parameters: (1) in-situ,
80 (2) air-based, and (3) space-based measurements, the last two of which are considered as Remote
81 Sensing (RS) techniques. Today, there are some global and local environmental services that
82 ensure consistent and reliable access to a range of in-situ OWQ data for the purpose of service
83 production and validation. For instance, the in-situ Thematic Assembly Centra (TAC) of the

84 Copernicus marine service (<https://marine.copernicus.eu>), which collects multi-source, multi-
85 platform, heterogenous data of the oceans , and the National Water Quality Data (NWQD) of
86 National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) (<https://coast.noaa.gov>), are main
87 platforms for accessing in-situ data of ocean characteristics.

88 Although in-situ measurements are the most accurate techniques for OWQ assessment, it is usually
89 time-consuming, risky, expensive, and labor-intensive, especially over large ocean environments,
90 to collect these data. Moreover, most of the in-situ measurement services measure or predict just
91 a few WQ parameters, such as water temperature, chlorophyll, and salinity. These facts, along with
92 the inconsistency in the data measurements by different organizations as well as the lack of spatial
93 and temporal continuity, make in-situ measurements less applicable in many situations (Ritchie,
94 Zimba et al. 2003). On the other hand, although RS techniques are not as accurate as in-situ
95 measurements, they can effectively mitigate most of the limitations of field-based methods.
96 Additionally, spaceborne RS systems provide cost-effective and frequent observations over the
97 oceans and facilitate OWQ monitoring over time. RS systems measure the water radiation or
98 emission at different parts of the electromagnetic spectrum, which are directly influenced by some
99 of the OWQ substances. The underlying concept is that various domains of the electromagnetic
100 spectrum received from different sources of light into the water are selectively absorbed or
101 backscattered by in-water constituents at different intensities (Liu, Islam et al. 2003). Water
102 radiance is affected by a variety of factors, including lighting conditions, water depth, bottom
103 reflectance, and OWQ substances (Parsons, Amani et al. 2021). Consequently, studying the water-
104 leaving radiance captured by RS instruments (after correcting and removing the scattered energy
105 from the atmosphere) can reveal different information about OWQ.

106 The major difference between airborne and spaceborne RS is the platform on which a particular

107 sensor is placed. Due to differences in the platform, they also differ in the distance between the
108 sensor and the object of interest, periodicity of image acquisition, timing of image acquisition, as
109 well as location and extent of coverage (Lamy 2019). Each of the airborne and spaceborne RS
110 techniques has its own advantages and limitations for assessing OWQ (Santos 2000, Ritchie,
111 Zimba et al. 2003). For example, the shorter distance of airborne platforms to water bodies usually
112 results in accurate measurements of WQ parameters at a better spatial resolution. However, the
113 use of aerial sensors in ocean studies is relatively inefficient mainly due to the vastness and
114 remoteness of the oceans. Spaceborne systems are more applicable to OWQ monitoring due to
115 multiple factors, such as global coverage, frequent and sustained acquisitions from multiple
116 platforms, availability of open-access data, and ready-to-use products (Ikeda 1995). Many studies
117 have so far investigated the applications of RS for WQ assessment (Brando and Dekker 2003, Liu,
118 Islam et al. 2003, Ritchie, Zimba et al. 2003, Usali and Ismail 2010, Gholizadeh, Melesse et al.
119 2016). Most of these studies have focused on WQ mapping in shallow waters, including rivers,
120 ponds, wetlands, and other inland water bodies, rather than the oceans. However, due to the
121 complexity of OW, the optimal methods applied for estimating the quality of shallow water cannot
122 be effectively extended to assess OWQ.

123 With this introduction, the main goal of this review paper is discussing the RS systems and
124 techniques as well as their advantages and limitations in mapping and monitoring the OWQ
125 parameters. Given the multiple advantages of spaceborne observations in mapping and monitoring
126 OWQ, we only focused on spaceborne RS systems and techniques in this review paper. This study
127 has five sections. After the introduction section, the main idea behind RS techniques for OWQ
128 studies as well as RS theories and algorithms are explained in Section 2. The RS systems that have
129 been applied to derive OWQ parameters, as well as their benefits and limitations are discussed in

130 [Section 3](#). [Section 4](#) discusses various OWQ parameters that are quantifiable using RS methods.
131 Finally, conclusions are provided in [Section 5](#).

132 **1.1. Method of review**

133 There are a variety of qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-design approaches and guidelines to
134 prepare literature review papers. The systematic, semi-systematic, and integrative approaches are
135 the three broad types of procedures often utilized ([Snyder 2019](#)). All types of strategies and
136 approaches can be useful and appropriate depending on the research topic, the purpose of the
137 review, and research questions. Various systematic methods have been used for the preparation of
138 review papers in the environmental and engineering fields. However, in this study, obtaining a
139 comprehensive bibliographic database using a systematic technique was a challenge because there
140 are many articles that examined the WQ parameters in shallow water bodies, including rivers,
141 lakes, wetlands, and temporary water bodies using RS techniques. On the other hand, most studies
142 that studied the quality of deep-water bodies in the sea and the waters leading to the ocean have
143 not mentioned "ocean" in their publications. Although the WQ parameters in the open ocean are
144 similar to those in shallow water, many of the parameters measured in shallow water using RS
145 systems are irrelevant in the oceans. Consequently, to have competent research into RS potential
146 in OWQ estimation, articles with shallow water case studies must be excluded from bibliographic
147 database. Another issue with conducting systematic approaches in this study was assessing quality
148 proxies in ocean pollution studies. Generally, measuring some specific parameters of water,
149 usually called quality parameters, which deviate slightly from the physical and chemical OWQ
150 parameters, is effective method of monitoring ocean pollution. This issue, along with different lists
151 of OWQ parameters considered in different research studies, made the systematic search not
152 sufficient for this review. Consequently, we employed a combined systematic and semi-systematic

153 technique in this study to avoid the above-mentioned issues. To this end, we employed the
154 systematic searching method used by [Mirmazloumi, Moghimi et al. \(2021\)](#) to prepare the initial
155 documents for content analysis. We conducted a title, abstract, and keyword systematic literature
156 search of relevant articles in the Clarivate Analytics Web of Science to find conference and journal
157 papers published between 1975 and 2022. The first literature search was conducted using the words
158 of "water quality" and "ocean" mentioned in the title of papers. Later, we included "remote
159 sensing" in this search. In total, the first search resulted in 54 papers. Then, we removed the
160 category of pollution and only used the keywords of the oceanographic, remote sensing,
161 engineering ocean, and water resources (23 more relevant journals were separated from 54 papers).
162 After investigating these papers, the WQ parameters that are usually considered for ocean studies
163 and are quantizable using RS systems were identified and listed. Then, the names of the listed
164 OWQ parameters were used in the research. For example, all combinations of "chlorophyll" and
165 "remote sensing" were separately examined. Then, we added the "ocean" in the systematic
166 research, along with the name of OWQ parameters and "remote sensing". For example, we found
167 190 and 11 papers by searching the "Chlorophyll and remote sensing" and "Chlorophyll, remote
168 sensing, and ocean" in the title, abstract, and keywords of the studies published in Web of Science
169 Core Collection, respectively. After each search, the papers were analyzed from the perspective of
170 the study area to exclude those which were not related to the oceans. Later, all sensors utilized in
171 these papers were listed to determine the various RS systems for the OWQ experiments. The names
172 of the listed sensors were also used with the names of the OWQ parameters in the systematic search
173 to found more articles based on the RS systems. It should be mentioned that official websites of
174 RS systems were also searched to include more studies related to OWQ. Moreover, duplicate
175 papers obtained by various combinations were found and removed using title filtering.

176 Furthermore, the papers with no source file and extraneous documents were eliminated. Finally,
177 the remaining papers were investigated from different points of view to write the various sections
178 of this review paper.

179 **2. OWQ: RS theory and methods**

180 Before starting with the theories and algorithms applied for mapping OWQ using RS data, we first
181 exemplified how satellite data can be used for OWQ monitoring. [Figure 1](#) schematically illustrates
182 the interaction between RS sensors and the main optically active substances in the atmosphere and
183 OW. Generally, the spectral properties of the ocean are divided into the Inherent Optical Properties
184 (IOPs) and Apparent Optical Properties (AOPs) ([Dickey, Lewis et al. 2006](#), [Ioannou, Gilerson et
185 al. 2011](#)). IOPs (e.g., absorption coefficient and total scattering) describe the characteristics of
186 water ([Hoge, Vodacek et al. 1993](#)). IOPs can be quantified in the laboratory using water samples,
187 as well as in-situ measurements in the ocean. AOPs (e.g., radiance and downwelling plane
188 irradiance), which are measured using optical RS systems ([Figure 1](#)), depend on the IOPs and the
189 geometric structure of the radiance distribution (e.g., atmospheric situation, surface water
190 structure, and wind speed) ([Gordon, Brown et al. 1975](#), [Morel and Loisel 1998](#)).

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192 Figure 1: The interaction of the primary optically active chemicals in the atmosphere and Ocean Water (OW) with
 193 Remote Sensing (RS) sensors.

194 AOPs are not only affected by the water constituents but also display useful descriptors of the
 195 water body. These two types of spectral properties can be related by the Radiative Transfer (RT)

196 models (Dickey, Lewis et al. 2006). IOPs are directly impacted by OWQ substances and do not
197 depend on the ambient light field. The main idea is that all particles added to pure OW have specific
198 physical and chemical characteristics that directly affect the spectral properties of the ocean.
199 Moreover, AOPs are convertible to the IOPs using the RT models, meaning that they are also
200 influenced by the OWQ parameters (Dickey, Lewis et al. 2006). Consequently, investigating the
201 AOPs and IOPs of OW is one of the most common methods for mapping and monitoring OWQ
202 parameters. There are a vast number of studies that have discussed the relationship between the
203 OWQ parameters, AOPs and IOPs (Gordon, Brown et al. 1975, Kirk 1984, Lee, Carder et al. 2002,
204 Huang, Chen et al. 2015).

205 Based on the AOPs estimated using optical RS systems, OW can be classified into two categories:
206 case-1 (i.e., open ocean) and case-2 (i.e., coastal, estuarine, and shelf regions) (Morel and Prieur
207 1977, Gordon and Morel 2012). Case-1 refers to the open ocean environment, which is deeper than
208 the shallow coastal seas (Morel and Prieur 1977). According to (Morel and Prieur 1977), the
209 spectral properties of the case-1 waters are mainly determined by phytoplankton, which is
210 represented by the Chl-a concentration (Behrenfeld, Boss et al. 2005). Thus, the corresponding
211 OWQ studies are limited to retrieving the Chl-a concentration, which can mainly be derived from
212 the spectral bands within the blue to green regions (Gholizadeh, Melesse et al. 2016). On the other
213 hand, case-2 refers to the shallow coastal waters. The spectral properties of the case-2 waters,
214 which are more turbid than the open ocean, are affected by other optically active constituents, such
215 as mineral particles, CDOM, and microbubbles (Gordon and Morel 2012). Compared to open
216 ocean, remotely sensed measurements of the OWQ in case-2 are more challenging and subjected
217 to different errors because of the larger number of water constituents that affect the AOPs of coastal
218 regions (Xiong, Ran et al. 2020). It is worth noting that most OWQ studies have focused on coastal

219 areas and bays due to the importance of these complex environments in biological activity, marine
220 ecosystems, climate systems, seafood, and human livelihoods (i.e., employment, commerce,
221 cultural and social interaction, and artistic activities).

222 OWQ studies using RS techniques began in the early 1970s, shortly after the surge in satellite
223 development (Ritchie, Zimba et al. 2003). As mentioned before, the intuitive idea behind OWQ
224 estimation is that water constituents that influence OWQ affect the radiation characteristics of
225 surface waters measured by RS systems. This idea led to the emergence of bio-optical modeling,
226 in which water constituents are related to the recorded radiometric variables of the water surface
227 (e.g., radiance and irradiance reflectance types), as follows (Giardino, Candiani et al. 2012):

$$Y=f(X) \quad \begin{cases} Y=A+B \times X \\ Y=AB^X \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

228 where Y and X are the RS measurements (i.e., radiance, reflectance, energy) and the OWQ
229 parameters (i.e., TSS, Chl-a), respectively (Ritchie, Zimba et al. 2003). It should be noted that two
230 different equations of Eq. (1) are the proxies for the linear and nonlinear relationships between RS
231 data and OWQ parameters, both of which have been employed to illustrate distinctive
232 characteristics of water. Several techniques have so far been proposed and evaluated to extract the
233 corresponding relationship considering the OWQ parameters that need to be studied, the type of
234 water bodies, the scale of the study area, and several external environmental parameters that can
235 affect the spectral or thermal properties of surface waters. These techniques can be classified into
236 four categories: empirical, semi-empirical, analytical, and semi-analytical models (Gholizadeh,
237 Melesse et al. 2016). Figure 2 illustrates the schematic flowcharts of the empirical, semi-empirical,
238 and semi-analytical techniques for OWQ monitoring. More details of each method are also
239 provided below.

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Figure 2. Schematic flowchart of the empirical, semi-empirical, and semi-analytical techniques for WQ studies. a and b represent the absorption and scattering coefficients of a spectrum domain of the energy, respectively. The reflectance measurements of the spectral bands of RS systems are indicated by R_{RS} . If more than one spectral band is used to estimate OWQ parameters, R_1 , R_2 , R_3 , and R_4 are used instead of R_{RS} . In this regard, g_i is a proxy of the coefficients with different values depending on the spectral bands used to calculate various OWQ parameters.

Empirical models primarily involve statistical analyses between the sampled OWQ measurements and remotely sensed AOPs of water (Chen, Chen et al. 2022). In these models, the bands or band combinations that have the highest correlation with OWQ parameters are first identified and selected as the RS data (Blondeau-Patissier, Gower et al. 2014). Then, the statistical relationship between the OWQ parameters and the selected RS datasets is determined using different techniques, such as Linear Regression (LR), non-LR, and empirical orthogonal function analysis (Carpenter and Carpenter 1983).

Semi-empirical methods are similar to empirical models, with the difference that they integrate the water spectral theory with traditional statistical techniques. In other words, in semi-empirical

255 approaches, after analyzing the IOPs of a WQ parameter, the most appropriate method and band
256 combinations are selected to retrieve the corresponding WQ parameter from RS images
257 ([Subramaniam, Brown et al. 2001](#)). Recent advances in hyperspectral RS technology have
258 accelerated the improvement of the semi-empirical methods by estimating the impacts of different
259 water constituents on the IOPs of water bodies at different wavelengths ([Shafique, Fulk et al. 2003](#),
260 [Liew, Choo et al. 2019](#)). A comprehensive list of the various spectral bands and band combinations
261 that have been utilized for quantifying different OWQ parameters can be found in ([Gholizadeh](#),
262 [Melesse et al. 2016](#)).

263 Generally, the empirical and semi-empirical models are relatively easy to implement and are
264 suitable for identifying the parameters that represent distinctive absorption features, such as Chl-a
265 ([Xiong, Ran et al. 2020](#)). For example, in the case-1 waters, where phytoplankton is the sole
266 determinant of the optical properties of the water, employing a simple empirical or semi-empirical
267 model usually provides an accurate relationship between Chl-a and RS measurements ([Gordon](#)
268 [and Morel 2012](#)). Nonetheless, empirical methods are usually not suitable for estimating OWQ
269 parameters in the case-2 waters due to the various constituents that affect the optical and thermal
270 properties of water ([Shanmugam 2011](#)). Furthermore, the application of the relationship between
271 water constituents and RS data extracted from the empirical and semi-empirical approaches is
272 limited to the study areas and is not applicable to other water bodies, even with similar conditions
273 ([Bierman, Lewis et al. 2011](#), [Mouw, Greb et al. 2015](#)). Therefore, although these methods are easy
274 to implement, they are not suitable for determining OWQ parameters in many areas, especially in
275 the coastal OW ([Chen, Chen et al. 2022](#)).

276 Unlike the empirical and semi-empirical models, analytical methods are based on the RT theory,
277 which quantifies the IOPs of OWQ parameters. In fact, analytical models estimate the

278 concentrations of the constituents of the water using a ratio of their absorption and backscattering
279 coefficients (Odermatt, Gitelson et al. 2012). So far, several analytical models have been
280 developed to extract spatial and temporal patterns of OWQ. These models can simultaneously
281 determine all constituents of water if a large number of in-situ data and comprehensive knowledge
282 about the IOPs of the OWQ parameters are available. However, this level of in-situ measurements
283 and comprehensive knowledge is not easy to access. This issue, along with the complexity of
284 analytical approaches in terms of their theory and implementation, makes them less applicable for
285 retrieving OWQ parameters using RS images (Gholizadeh, Melesse et al. 2016).

286 Methods that co-exploit analytical and empirical models are known as semi-analytical techniques,
287 in which more simplified RT equations (e.g., two-, three-, and four-band models) are considered
288 to estimate the concentrations of constituents (Mouw, Greb et al. 2015). Rising interest in the field
289 of semi-analytical methods combined with multivariate statistical analysis approaches, such as
290 Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (Yang, Zhao et al. 2020), Inverse Distance Weighted (IDW)
291 (Bagyaraj, Ramkumar et al. 2013), Cluster Analysis (CA) (Kamble and Vijay 2011, Torrecilla,
292 Stramski et al. 2011), Discriminant Analysis (DA) (Lei, Zhang et al. 2016), and Factor Analysis
293 (FA) (Sathyendranath, Prieur et al. 1989), has considerably facilitated the study of different OWQ
294 parameters using RS measurements (Bierman, Lewis et al. 2011).

295 Besides the traditional band math techniques, Machine Learning (ML) methods have become
296 popular in recent years. These methods duplicate the human brain's processes and converts the
297 OWQ estimation problem into a computer-recognizable input method. Many benefits of ML
298 methods compared to nonlinear regression fitting models have increased their application in
299 various studies. Generally, ML methods can automatically learn from various datasets and then
300 construct a model based on minimizing the variance between the training samples and prediction

301 values (Amani, Macdonald et al. 2021, Hassan and Woo 2021). These methods, along with RS
302 data, are powerful approaches for the routine assessment of spatial and temporal variations of
303 OWQ parameters (Wagle, Acharya et al. 2020). Additionally, thanks to coping with nonlinearity
304 and other complex regression problems, ML methods usually have more advantages for estimating
305 OWQ parameters compared to empirical methods (Verrelst, Muñoz et al. 2012). Generally, ML is
306 classified into different categories based on the learning type (supervised or unsupervised) and
307 learning model (classification, regression, clustering, or dimensionality reduction) (Wagle,
308 Acharya et al. 2020). Wagle, Acharya et al. (2020) outlines a general workflow of estimating WQ
309 parameters using ML algorithms and RS data. Based on this study, the Artificial Neural Network
310 (ANN) (Chen, Chen et al. 2021), K-nearest neighbors (KNN) (Alevizos 2020), Support Vector
311 Machine (SVM) (Chen, Li et al. 2004), Deep Neural Network (DNN) (Medina-Lopez and Ureña-
312 Fuentes 2019), and Random Forest (RF) (Sagawa, Yamashita et al. 2019) are the most commonly
313 used ML algorithms to measure coastal water properties and OWQ.

314 **3. RS Systems, their benefits and limitations**

315 OWQ studies require a monitoring network that provides frequent observations with a suitable
316 spatial resolution over the large and remote ocean environments. During the past few decades,
317 observations from various satellites have been used to estimate different OWQ parameters. Some
318 of these systems are equipped with Ocean Color Radiometry (OCR) sensors to provide water-
319 leaving radiance or reflectance over open ocean regions (case-1 waters), while the others, which
320 usually contain a higher spatial resolution, are mainly employed over terrestrial regions and are
321 suitable for coastal studies (Parsons, Amani et al. 2021).

322 The RS systems can generally be divided into two groups of passive and active. Both passive and
323 active RS systems can effectively acquire physical, chemical, thermal, and biological

324 characteristics of OWQ parameters (Gholizadeh, Melesse et al. 2016, Toming, Kutser et al. 2017).
 325 Table 2 summarizes the commonly used RS systems for OWQ assessment along with their
 326 characteristics. More information about some of these RS systems is also provided below. It should
 327 be noted that since previous studies have discussed all of the RS systems used in ocean studies
 328 (Amani, Ghorbanian et al. 2021, Amani, Mohseni et al. 2022), we only focused on the RS systems
 329 which are commonly used in OWQ assessment studies.

330 Table 2. The main characteristics of the RS systems for OWQ studies (mi: minutes, h: hours, p: present, km:
 331 kilometer, m: meter, d: day)

System type	sensor	Platform	Mission duration	Spatial resolution (m)	Revisit time (d)	Spectral bands
Optical/thermal (multi-bands)	CZCS	Nimbus-7	1978-1986	825	6	6 bands (443-1250 nm)
	OCTS	ADEOS	1996-1997	700	3	12 bands (400-1200 nm)
	MSS/TM/ETM+	Landsat 5 to 7	1982-p	15,30	15, 30, 120	8 bands (450–1040 nm)
	SeaWiFS	AKA SeaStar	1997-2010	1 km, 4 km	2	8 bands (402-885nm)
	OSA	IKONOS	1999-2015	1-4	3	5 bands (450-900 nm)
	MODIS	Terra/ Aqua	1999- p	250, 500, 1000	1-2	36 bands (405-2155 nm)
	MISR	Terra	1999-p	275	2, 9	4 bands (425-886 nm)
	Hyperion	EO-1	2000-2017	30	16	242 bands (350-2570 nm)
	CHRIS	PROBA-1	2001-p	17 m	18	18 bands (400–1050 nm)
	MERIS	Envisat-1	2002-2012	200, 1200	1	15 bands (390-1040 nm)
	HRG	SPOT 5	2002-2015	2.5, 5, 10, 20	5	5 bands (500-1750 nm)
	GIS-MS	GeoEye-1	2008-p	1.65	2	4 bands (450-920 nm)
	HICO	ISS	2009-2014	90	10	128 bands (350-1080 nm)
	WorldView-2	Digital Globe	2009-p	0.46, 1.85	~1	9 bands (400–1040 nm)
	OCM-2	Oceansat-2	2009-p	300	2, 3	8 bands (402-885 nm)
	GOCI	COMS/KOMPSAT-2	2010- p	500	~3 h	8 bands (412- 865 nm)
	VIIRS	Suomi/NOAA-20	2011-p	375, 750	1	22 bands (412-1201 nm)
	OLI/TIRS	Landsat-8	2013-p	15, 30, 100	16	11 bands (430-2290 nm)
	AHI	Himawari-8&9, GOES	2014-p	500, 1000, 2000	10 mi	16 bands (470-13300 nm)
	WorldView-3	Digital Globe	2014-p	0.31, 1.24, 3.7	1, 4.5	17 (400–2365 nm)
MSI	Sentinel-2 (A/B)	2015-p	10, 60	5	13 bands (442-2202.4 nm)	
OLCI	Sentinel-3 (A/B)	2016-p	300	1	21 bands (400-2130 nm)	

TIR radiometer	SGLI Hawkeye	GCOM-C SeaHawk	2017-p 2018-p	250, 500, 1000 120	2, 4 ~1	19 bands (380-12000 nm) 8 bands (402-885 nm)
	ASTER	Terra	1990-p	15, 30, 90	16	5 bands (8125-11650 nm)
	AVHRR-3	NOAA/METOP	1998-p	1090 (4000)	11	2 bands (10300-12500 nm)
Microwave Radiometers	ABI	GOES	2016-p	500, 1000, 2000	5-15 mi	16 bands (5770-13600 nm)
	ESMR	Nimbus-5, 6	1972-1983	2.5 km	1	1 band (19 GHz)
	SMMR	NIMBUS-7, Seasat	1978-1994	2.7, 5.4, 8.5, 4.9 km	4	5 bands (6.63 to 37 GHz)
	IKAR (D, N, P)	Priroda-MIR	1996-2001	5, 1.5, 2.6, 6, 7.5 km	1.7	5 bands (7.5 to 89.0 GHz)
	TMI	TRMM	1997-2015	4400 (45000)	0.5	5 bands (10.7 to 85.5 GHz)
	AMSR	ADEOS-II	2002-2003	5 km, 10 km	4	7 bands (6.925 to 89 GHz)
	AMSR-E	Aqua	2002-p	5 km, 10 km	16	6 bands (6.92 to 89 GHz)
	SSMIS	DMSP-F16	2003-2019	13, 15, 43, 69	1	4 bands (19.35 to 85.5 GHz)
	WindSat	Coriolis	2003-p	25000	8	5 bands (6.8 to 37 GHz)
	MIRAS	SMOS	2009-p	3.5-50 km	3	1 band (1.4 GHz)
	SAC-D	SAC-D (Aquarius)	2011-2015	7 (100)	7	1 band (1.413 GHz)
	AMSR2	GCOM-W1	2012-p	5-10 km	2	7 bands (6.925 to 89 GHz)
	GMI	GPM Core	2014-p	3000	2	2 bands (10, 183 GHz)

332

333 Sensors that have both optical and thermal spectral bands can be considered the main RS
334 instruments for ocean and sea related studies (White, Amani et al. 2021). These sensors provide
335 valuable information of OW properties at high spatial and temporal resolutions. Most of the
336 passive systems for OWQ studies have sun-synchronous orbits, positioned on a near-polar orbit at
337 an altitude of 700–850 km above sea level. They also have global coverage with different revisit
338 times depending on the latitude and size of the swath. However, some of the passive systems are
339 geostationary satellites. Geostationary satellites provide coverage of a specific part of the earth
340 with a very high temporal resolution (e.g., several minutes) and lower spatial resolution (Pocha
341 2012). For example, the Geostationary Ocean Color Imager (GOCI) was launched on board
342 COMS/KOMPSAT-2 by South Korea in June 2010 as the first geostationary OC sensor. The
343 corresponding scenes cover an area of 2500 km × 2500 km in northeast Asia centered at the Korean

344 Peninsula. GOCI is the only geostationary satellite with the capability of OC measurements with
345 a temporal resolution of 1 hour and a spatial resolution of 500 m (Yuan, Jalón-Rojas et al. 2019).

346 Regarding the spectral bands, various RS systems have different capabilities for assessing OWQ
347 parameters. Generally, the capability of an RS system for OWQ assessment is primarily based on
348 the differences in spectral reflectance of clean water as well as mineral and organic materials (Liu,
349 Islam et al. 2003). Assessing the relationship between OWQ parameters and radiance or
350 reflectance values observed by RS systems is the main step in most OWQ modeling. This is
351 because a small concentration of OWQ parameters can affect the reflectance of OW received by
352 RS systems. For example, MEdium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MERIS) on board Envisat-
353 1 contains a 709 nm channel with a spatial resolution of 250–300 m along with other bands in the
354 visible to Near Infrared (NIR) parts of the electromagnetic spectrum, which makes it useful to
355 retrieve algal blooms (Gower, King et al. 2008). In turbid waters, the light absorption coefficient
356 of algal blooms is greater than that of pure water around the red absorption peak of Chl-a, so
357 measurement of reflectance near 700 nm and its ratio to 670 nm has proved useful for detecting
358 algal blooms (Gitelson, Dall'Olmo et al. 2008).

359 Ocean and Land Colour Instrument (OLCI) on board the Sentinel-3A/B is also a follow-up
360 program of the MERIS mission. OLCI was planned to support OWQ assessment studies with 21
361 spectral bands varying from 400 to 1020 nm in the Short-Wave Infrared (SWIR) (Shen, Zhou et
362 al. 2014, Toming, Kutser et al. 2017). Additionally, the Second-Generation GLobal Imager
363 (SGLI), launched on GCOM-C by the Japan Aerospace eXploration Agency (JAXA), was
364 designed with 11 nadir channels in the visible to NIR parts of the spectrum. This system supports
365 the improved characterization of turbidity, absorbing aerosols, CDOM, and phytoplankton (Ogata,
366 Toratani et al. 2017). Furthermore, the Sea-Viewing Wide Field-of-View Sensor (SeaWiFS) on

367 board AKA SeaStar was a part of the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA)'s
368 Earth science enterprise. The main objective of the SeaWiFS project was to provide quantitative
369 data on global ocean bio-optical properties and monitor ocean Chl-a concentrations from space
370 ([Acker, Shen et al. 2002](#)). However, the data of SeaWiFS have been used for collecting many other
371 environmental-parameters, including the Particulate Organic Carbon (POC) concentration,
372 Particulate Inorganic Carbon (PIC) concentration, Photo synthetically Active Radiation (PAR),
373 Normalized Fluorescence Line Height (NFLH), and Normalized Difference Vegetation
374 Index (NDVI).

375 Although all the above-mentioned RS systems have a high potential for monitoring OC properties,
376 they contain low or medium spatial resolution. As noted above, higher-resolution sensors, such as
377 the Operational Land Imager (OLI) onboard Landsat-8 and the MultiSpectral Instrument (MSI)
378 onboard Sentinel-2, were mainly designed for terrestrial applications. However, they offer great
379 potential for OWQ studies at a 10-100 m resolution over coastal and fresh-water areas ([Bresciani,
380 Cazzaniga et al. 2018](#)). In addition to OLI and MSI, the data of other high spatial-resolution
381 satellites, such as GeoEye-1, Worldview-2/3, IKONOS, and SPOT-5 have frequently been applied
382 to monitor several water features, such as turbidity, sediment plumes, floating vegetation and
383 phytoplankton information at coastal regions ([Gholizadeh, Melesse et al. 2016](#), [Groom,
384 Sathyendranath et al. 2019](#)).

385 The Thermal InfraRed (TIR) radiometers, such as the Moderate Resolution Imaging
386 Spectroradiometer (MODIS), Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection
387 Radiometer (ASTER), Advanced Very High-Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR-3), and Advanced
388 Baseline Imager (ABI) with 16, 5, 3, and 10 TIR bands, respectively, have also been used for
389 assessing OWQ with an adequate temporal resolution. It should be noted that hyperspectral images

390 usually provide data with a better spatial and spectral resolutions for OWQ studies, but the number
391 of these systems is limited, and the corresponding data are relatively expensive.

392 In addition to the optical/thermal sensors, there is a considerable amount of literature on estimating
393 the salinity and temperature of OWQ using passive Microwave (MW) sensors. Passive MW
394 sensors provide accurate measurements of the ocean's salinity and temperature. This is mainly
395 because the emission, measured by passive MW systems, is sensitive to permittivity (dielectric
396 constant), which depends on the water temperature and salinity (Meissner, Wentz et al. 2016).
397 Among the spaceborne passive MW sensors applied to OWQ studies, Soil Moisture Active Passive
398 (SMAP), Soil Moisture Ocean Salinity (SMOS), and Aquarius were specifically developed for
399 global monitoring of SSS (Dinnat, Le Vine et al. 2019). Even though SMAP, SMOS, and Aquarius
400 missions have several systematic differences, all of them utilize the L-band radiometer as their
401 primary instrument to retrieve salinity and brightness temperature information over the global
402 ocean (Olmedo, Gabarró et al. 2018). An increasing number of studies have validated their
403 products on a global scale and have shown the great promise of these products to monitor the
404 salinity and temperature in the ocean (Lagerloef, Kao et al. 2015, Olmedo, Gabarró et al. 2018,
405 Dinnat, Le Vine et al. 2019).

406 Among various spectral domains of RS data (i.e., visible, NIR, TIR, passive and active MW), the
407 optical (i.e., visible and NIR) and thermal domains of the electromagnetic spectrum are more
408 useful for assessing OWQ, respectively (Zheng and DiGiacomo 2017). Moreover, Advanced
409 Himawari Imager (AHI) on board Himawari-8&9, OLI onboard Landsat-8, Thematic Mapper Plus
410 (ETM+) onboard Landsat-7, and MODIS onboard Terra/Aqua are the most widely used sensors
411 for oceanography applications and OWQ assessment (Wang and Yang 2019). Additionally, Fusing
412 datasets from different resources can overcome several limitations of RS methods (Chapron,

413 [Garello et al. 2008](#)). However, fusing should carefully be implemented because different datasets
414 can contain various spatial and spectral characteristics.

415 Although RS data can effectively be utilized for monitoring long-term OWQ parameters, accurate
416 and sufficient in-situ samples usually improve OWQ assessment. However, in-situ measurements
417 over the oceans are expensive and labor-intensive ([Wang and Yang 2019](#)). Thus, RS systems
418 provide better opportunities for OWQ assessment in many cases. Despite the benefits of RS
419 systems mentioned above, there are still several limitations preventing obtaining highly accurate
420 OWQ parameters. Most RS-based models for retrieving OWQ parameters are dependent on the
421 number of in-situ samples and, therefore, the lack of in-situ measurements reduces the accuracy of
422 these techniques ([Daya 2004](#)). Furthermore, the coarse spatial resolution of passive geostationary
423 satellites and radiometers (i.e., greater than 1km) is a limitation to assessing OWQ parameters,
424 especially in the case-2 waters. Considering the extent and remoteness of oceans in the case-1
425 waters, the available RS systems properly assess open ocean WQ parameters, including Chl-a,
426 SSS, and SST. Moreover, some of the RS systems have long revisit times, especially over regions
427 that are prone to frequent cloud/rain ([Daya 2004](#)). Finally, for long-term OWQ analysis, big RS
428 data (more than a petabyte) may need to be downloaded, processed, analyzed, and interpreted. This
429 brings several new challenges. In this regard, various cloud computing platforms, such as Google
430 Earth Engine (GEE), have been developed ([Amani, Ghorbanian et al. 2020](#)).

431 **4. OWQ parameters assessed by RS**

432 As mentioned, the OWQ parameters are directly affected by the type of water and, thus, are
433 different for the case-1 and case-2 waters ([Schalles 2006](#)). Given the case-1 water (open ocean),
434 Chl-a, CDOM, and detritus degradation parameters (i.e., optically active variables) are considered
435 as the OWQ parameters and are measured using optical/thermal RS techniques ([Gordon and Morel](#)

436 [2012](#)). Furthermore, in the case-1 waters, some other parameters, such as SSS and SST, which can
437 be measured using MW systems, have been studied ([Swift 1980](#), [Ward 2006](#), [Martin 2014](#)). In the
438 case-2 waters (e.g., coastal waters), SDD, turbidity, TSS, DOC, TP, DO, Biochemical Oxygen
439 Demand (BOD), and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) are commonly studied using RS
440 techniques. Based on our knowledge, there is no literature review on monitoring these WQ
441 parameters over open oceans. Therefore, we presented a comprehensive review of the retrieval of
442 these parameters in the open ocean. In the following subsection, the RS techniques that have been
443 applied to derive and monitor the most important OWQ parameters are explained.

444 **4.1.Chlorophyll-a (Chl-a)**

445 Chl-a, a specific form of chlorophyll in oxygenic photosynthesis, is defined as a proxy for
446 phytoplankton concentration in surface waters ([O'Reilly, Maritorena et al. 1998](#), [Bukata, Jerome
447 et al. 2018](#)). Chl-a is also considered as one of the most important optically active variables in open
448 oceans and coastal areas ([Blondeau-Patissier, Gower et al. 2014](#)). The literature has demonstrated
449 that an increase in Chl-a concentration leads to a decrease in the spectral response at short
450 wavelengths (e.g., at ~400 nm) ([Ritchie, Cooper et al. 1990](#), [Dekker and Peters 1993](#), [George 1997](#),
451 [Brivio, Giardino et al. 2001](#)). [Figure 3a](#) shows the reflectance of the case-1 water with three
452 different Chl-a concentrations (i.e., 0.1, 1 and 10) and for four sets of viewing directions. The
453 information about Chl-a concentrations in each chart is mentioned as a single number. Moreover,
454 the characteristics of the viewing directions are represented as a set of two angle values, including
455 the azimuth angle of the radiance and the azimuth angle of the observed reflectance, respectively.
456 This figure shows that the spectral characteristics of the case-1 water are much more sensitive to
457 Chl-a than to external environmental conditions and viewing directions. As such, in the same
458 viewing direction, the value of Chl-a concentration significantly affects the spectral properties of

459 the water at two spectral wavelengths. In fact, the reflectance values at ~400 nm and ~550 nm
 460 decrease and increase by increasing the Chl-a values, respectively. Figure 3b also displays the
 461 reflectance spectra of seven water samples taken at wavelengths of 440 and 670 nm on March 11,
 462 2008, in Lake Kinneret, Israel (Yacobi 2012). Because they all have the same Chl-a concentration,
 463 all seven samples of the Lake Kinneret water have the same location of absorption troughs
 464 (reflectance) and peaks (reciprocal reflectance).

465 Figure 3. (a) The absorption spectrum of samples of the case-1 water at various Chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) concentrations
 466 and viewing angles (Mobley, Boss et al. 2010), (b) the absorption spectrum of seven water samples of the Lake
 467 Kinneret water, Israel (Yacobi 2012).
 468

469 In the case-1 waters, which are characterized by simple optical properties (Sathyendranath and
 470 Platt 1997), Chl-a concentrations are generally retrieved using the empirical algorithms based on
 471 the ratio or differences of spectral reflectance at the blue and green regions of the spectrum with
 472 an uncertainty of 35% (Hu, Lee et al. 2012, O'Reilly and Werdell 2019). This scenario is slightly
 473 different in turbid coastal waters, which are optically complex and significantly variable. In coastal
 474 areas, the retrieval algorithms based on the Optical Water Type (OWT) are usually used to map
 475 Chl-a due to the intermingled optical signals of OWQ parameters (McKee, Cunningham et al.
 476 2007, Huang, Li et al. 2014, Sun, Hu et al. 2014, Neil, Spyrakos et al. 2019). In this regard, various

477 OC algorithms, including reflectance classification (Barnes, Hu et al. 2013), band-ratio (Keith,
478 Schaeffer et al. (2014), red-NIR spectral region (Gitelson, Schalles et al. 1999), band difference
479 (Gower, King et al. 2005), bio-optical (Tilstone, Peters et al. 2012), along with various indices,
480 such as Fluorescence Line Height (FLH) (Xing, Zhao et al. 2007), Maximum Chlorophyll Index
481 (MCI) (Gower, King et al. 2008), Floating Algae Index (FAI) (Hu, Cannizzaro et al. 2010), Scaled
482 Algae Index (SAI) (Garcia, Fearnas et al. 2013), and Color Index Algorithm (CIA) (Hu, Lee et al.
483 2012) have been developed to monitor the Chl-a of oceans. Table 3 shows several empirical
484 algorithms which have frequently been applied to estimate Chl-a concentration.

485 Table 3. The commonly used empirical algorithms for Chl-a estimation.

Algorithm	Formula	Reference
OC3E	$Chl_a = 10^{0.2521 - 2.2146 X + 1.5193 X^2 - 0.7702 X^3 - 0.4291 X^4}$ $X = \log\left(\frac{R_{490}}{R_{555}}\right)$	(O'Reilly, Maritorena et al. 2000)
OC4E	$Chl_a = 10^{0.3255 - 2.7677 X + 2.4409 X^2 - 1.1288 X^3 - 0.4990 X^4}$ $X = \log(\max(R_{443}, R_{490}, R_{510})/R_{555})$	(O'Reilly, Maritorena et al. 2000)
OC4Me	$Chl_a = 10^{0.4502748 - 3.259491 X + 3.522731 X^2 - 3.359422 X^3 + 0.949586 X^4}$ $X = \log(\max(R_{443}, R_{490}, R_{510})/R_{555})$	(Morel and Antoine 2011)
Gu2B	$Chl_a = 25.28 \times (R_{665}^{-1} \times R_{709})^2 + 14.85 \times (R_{665}^{-1} \times R_{709}) - 15.18$	(Gurlin, Gitelson et al. 2011)
G2B	$Chl_a = ((35.75 \times (R_{665}^{-1} \times R_{708})) - 19.30)^{1.124}$	(Gilerson, Gitelson et al. 2010)
G3B	$Chl_a = ((113.36 \times (R_{665}^{-1} - R_{708}^{-1}) \times R_{753}) + 16.45)^{1.124}$	(Gilerson, Gitelson et al. 2010)
SCI	$Chl_a = 0.057 \times X^{0.6327}$ $X = 2 \times R_{681} - R_{665} - R_{620} + 0.26229 \times (R_{620} - R_{681}) + 0.50413 \times (R_{560} - R_{681})$	(Le, Hu et al. 2013)
NDCI	$Chl_a = 14.039 + (86.115 \times NDCI) + (194.325 \times NDCI^2)$ $NDCI = (R_{708} - R_{665}) / (R_{708} + R_{665})$	(Mishra and Mishra 2012)
SUN	$\log_{10}^{Chl_a} = 0.118445 - 3.057611 \log_{10} X + 3.0986261 \log_{10}^2$ $X = [R_{443}/R_{555}][R_{412}/R_{490}]^{-0.8}$	(Sun, Guo et al. 2010)
OC3Mv6	$Chl_a = 10^{0.2424 - 2.5828 X + 1.7057 X^2 - 0.3415 X^3 - 0.8818 X^4}$ $X = \log_{10}(\max(R_{443}, R_{490})/R_{555})$	(Lewis, Mitchell et al. 2016)

486
487 In Table 3, the $R_{555,490,443, \dots}$ represents the RS reflectance at various wavelengths. A vast range of
488 satellites, such as MSS/TM/ ETM+ (on Landsat), AVHRR (on NOAA/METOP), MODIS on

489 (Terra/Aqua), MERIS (on Envisat-1) OLCI (on Sentinel-3A/B), ASTER (on Terra), and SeaWiFS
490 (on SeaStar), has been used to estimate ocean Chl-a concentration (see Section 3 for more details
491 of these systems). Thanks to the easy accessibility of various satellite data, different RS products
492 have been developed for retrieving ocean Chl-a with global coverage and adequate spatial and
493 temporal resolution. For example, Figure 4 illustrates a monthly mean Chl-a product retrieved
494 from the MODIS/Aqua satellite datasets between 2017-04 and 2022-02 over the globe. Since
495 phytoplankton has a greenish tint due to a photosynthetic pigment or Chl-a, this map depicts where
496 and how much phytoplankton was growing on a specific period.

497
498 Figure 4. The monthly mean values of Chl-a between 2017-04 and 2022-02 over the globe, generated from
499 MODIS/Aqua data (https://neo.gsfc.nasa.gov/archive/rgb/MY1DMM_CHLORA/).

500 Many studies have so far used RS data for Chl-a estimation. For instance, Wang, Zhou et al. (2010)
501 estimated the monthly mean values of Chl-a in the Pacific Ocean using the AVHRR and SeaWiFS
502 images. Furthermore, Smith, Lain et al. (2018) combined two different empirical algorithms using

503 the MERIS and OLCI imagery in southern Benguela. They utilized the blue-green algorithm and
504 the red-NIR band-ratio model. Additionally, a weighting strategy was considered between
505 different reflectance values, which yielded the superior performance of the proposed approach
506 compared to any single algorithm. [Gower and Borstad \(2004\)](#), [Gower and King \(2007\)](#), and [Zhao,
507 Xing et al. \(2010\)](#) also applied the FLH method developed by [Neville and Gower \(1977\)](#) for
508 mapping Chl-a using MODIS and MERIS datasets. They also compared the results obtained from
509 each sensor's data. They argued that the MERIS bands were better for measuring fluorescence.
510 [Cui, Zhang et al. \(2020\)](#) also developed a novel method for monitoring Chl-a in turbid coastal
511 waters. Nine empirical algorithms were tested and optimized for different water types using
512 MODIS data to accurately retrieve Chl-a. The results showed that their proposed approach reduced
513 the uncertainty of Chl-a estimation from 54% to 36% and proved the highest prediction
514 performance of the water classification with the optimal algorithm for each class in optically
515 complex waters. Finally, [Umbert, Guimbard et al. \(2020\)](#) extrapolated MODIS Chl-a products
516 using the MODIS SST measurements. To this end, Chl-a products were restored by estimating
517 local LR coefficients between Chl-a and SST. The results indicated that there was a strong positive
518 correlation between the original Chl-a data and the estimated values (ranging from 0.67 to 0.94)
519 in all seasons, except winter, when the correlation coefficients were low (between 0.15 and 0.47).

520 **4.2.Colored Dissolved Organic Matter (CDOM)**

521 CDOM, also known as chromophoric DOM, yellow substance, humic color, and gelbstoff
522 (sometimes called yellow matter or gilvin) ([Hoge, Vodacek et al. 1995](#)), is defined as an optically
523 measurable component of total DOM in water ([Brando and Dekker 2003](#)). The CDOM absorbs
524 short wavelengths of solar radiation, whereas pure water absorbs longer wavelengths of the red
525 light. By increasing CDOM, the absorption from ultra violet to blue spectrum increases and,

526 immediately, the absorption from red band decreases (Markager and Vincent 2000). Water with
527 various amounts of CDOM concentrations can have a wide range of colors (e.g., green-yellow and
528 brown). However, pure water usually appears blue with varying shades (Nelson and Coble 2009).
529 Nelson and Siegel (2002) reported that the CDOM's absorption coefficients at 440 nm are useful
530 as a representative of CDOM in the open oceans. In line with this theory, empirical algorithms,
531 such as band ratios at various wavelengths (e.g., R_{412}/R_{443} and R_{490}/R_{555}), have been developed to
532 estimate the CDOM (Morel and Gentili 2009). These methods are based on statistical relationships
533 between satellite-derived reflectance and CDOM, where linear or nonlinear regressions are applied
534 to satellite data. Several studies have proved the capability of the empirical band ratio algorithms
535 to monitor CDOM concentration using RS data, such as those collected by MODIS, SeaWiFS,
536 MERIS, and MSI (D'sa, Hu et al. 2002, D'sa and Ko 2008, Tehrani, D'Sa et al. 2013). In this
537 regard, Joshi and D'Sa (2015) developed an empirical band ratio algorithm using the bands 2 and
538 3 of MSS on board Landsat-5, in conjunction with meteorological and hydrological parameters, to
539 monitor seasonal CDOM distribution in Barataria Bay. They assessed seasonal variations, which
540 play a vital role in the algorithm's performance, especially in energetic and highly variable
541 environments like bays. The results showed the high performance of their model and the potential
542 of Landsat-5 data to estimate CDOM concentration. They also reported that applying the time
543 series of Landsat-5 data and reducing time difference between the in-situ and satellite observations
544 could improve the accuracy of their model.

545 In addition to empirical band ratio methods, semi-analytical algorithms, which are usually based
546 on a single exponential model with or without an offset, have widely been applied to describe
547 CDOM absorption as a function of wavelength in the visible domain. Some of these models are
548 Garver–Siegel–Maritorena (GSM), introduced by Garver and Siegel (1997) and further developed

549 by [Maritorena, Siegel et al. \(2002\)](#), are the Linear Matrix Model (LMM) developed by ([Hoge and](#)
550 [Lyon 1996](#)) and modified by ([Boss and Roesler 2006](#)), Quasi Analytical Algorithm (QAA)
551 developed by ([Lee, Carder et al. 2002](#)), and Carder-99 algorithm developed by ([Carder, Chen et](#)
552 [al. 1999](#)). These models are based on two key parameters of the spectral slope and the absorptions
553 at the reference wavelengths (mostly 412 or 443 nm) ([Shanmugam 2011](#)). Additionally,
554 [Shanmugam \(2011\)](#) introduced a new semi-analytical model for determining the absorption spectra
555 of CDOM using SeaWiFS data. In this method, two spectral slopes of an exponential curve fit, and
556 a hyperbolic curve fit, which was estimated using in-situ reflectance measurements in two
557 wavelengths of 443 and 555 nm, were employed. The evaluation model was carried out based on
558 the independent data and showed a Mean Relative Error (MRE) and Root Mean Square Error
559 (RMSE) of 5.64–3.55% and 0.203–0.318 for the NASA bio-Optical Marine Algorithm Dataset
560 (NOMAD) in-situ datasets, and 5.63–0.98% and 0.136–0.241 for the NOMAD-SeaWiFS satellite
561 datasets, respectively.

562 [Juhls, Overduin et al. \(2019\)](#) applied the absorption coefficient of CDOM (aCDOM) at 440 or 443
563 nm (aCDOM₄₄₀ or aCDOM₄₄₃) provided by the Ocean Color Remote Sensing (OCRS) algorithm
564 to estimate DOC concentration at high temporal and spatial resolutions over the Laptev Sea region
565 of the Arctic Ocean. To this end, they verified the performance of five OCRS algorithms, including
566 OLCI Neural Network Swarm (ONNS), MERIS Case-2 water algorithm (C2R), C2X algorithm,
567 the standard atmospheric correction of ONNS (C2RCC), and MERIS Case-2 water properties
568 processor (FUB/WeW), for estimating aCDOM. Since MERIS has a high spectral resolution and
569 Spectro-radiometric quality, they applied the data of this satellite to calculate DOC concentration
570 from the satellite-retrieved aCDOM. [Figure 5](#) shows the aCDOM product derived from five OCRS
571 algorithms. [Juhls, Overduin et al. \(2019\)](#) argued that the ONNS algorithm had the best performance

572 compared to in-situ aCDOM (correlation coefficient of 0.72). They also reported that ONNS-
 573 derived aCDOM₄₄₀, in contrast to other algorithms, was independent of the sediment
 574 concentration, making ONNS the most suitable aCDOM algorithm for the Laptev Sea region.

575
 576 Figure 5. The absorption coefficient of Colored Dissolved Organic Matter (CDOM) of water, which was measured
 577 using five OCRS algorithms (C2R, ONNS, C2RCC, C2X, and FUB/WeW) and MERIS mosaic data between 3
 578 August 2010 and 20 September 2010. In-situ aCDOM₄₄₃ is depicted in colorful squares (Juhls, Overduin et al.
 579 2019).

580 Furthermore, Keith, Schaeffer et al. (2014) retrieved Chl-a concentrations, CDOM, and turbidity
 581 in four Florida estuaries using atmospherically corrected Hyperspectral Imager for the Coastal
 582 Ocean (HICO) images and in-situ and laboratory data. Chl-a was estimated using the three-band
 583 approach with the form of $[\lambda_1^{-1} - \lambda_2^{-1}] \times \lambda_3$. In this method, two wavelengths in the NIR to red
 584 spectrum (λ_1, λ_2) were multiplied by the reflectance of a NIR band (λ_3). This method was also

585 employed by [Dall'Olmo, Gitelson et al. \(2005\)](#) to retrieve Chl-a concentration from SeaWiFS and
586 MODIS images. Two empirical models were applied to estimate CDOM using the HICO
587 reflectance data in the band 43 (646 nm) and the ratio of the red band (670 nm) and blue-green
588 band (490 nm), respectively. The results proved the efficiency of the empirical and semi-empirical
589 methods, showing that they could successfully retrieve the Chl-a and CDOM concentrations from
590 HICO hyperspectral images.

591 There have been several attempts to find appropriate ML models to determine CDOM. In this
592 regard, [Kishino, Tanaka et al. \(2005\)](#) investigated an ANN technique for CDOM retrieval using
593 ASTER data. [Ruescas, Hieronymi et al. \(2018\)](#) also applied five different ML methods, including
594 Regularized Linear Regression (RLR), RF regression, Kernel Ridge Regression (KRR), Gaussian
595 Process Regression (GPR), and SVM to estimate CDOM using Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3
596 simulated reflectance data. Their results showed that all models and band combinations had
597 reasonable results. However, the GPR approach had the most accurate results, especially when all
598 Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 simulated reflectance bands were used.

599 Different RS systems have been utilized to assess CDOM. Generally, Landsat-8 images are
600 considered essential data to derive CDOM parameters due to the new coastal/aerosol band (433–
601 453 nm), increased radiometric sensitivity from 8-bit to 16-bit data, and the atmospherically-
602 corrected surface reflectance data of the OLI/TIRS sensor onboard this satellite ([Slonecker, Jones
603 et al. 2016](#)). The three high spatial resolution bands of ASTER (on board Terra) in the visible and
604 NIR ranges are also very useful for estimating CDOM ([Kishino, Tanaka et al. 2005](#)). Although the
605 spatial resolution of the MODIS and SeaWiFS is too coarse in rivers, coastal outfalls, and small
606 lakes ([Slonecker, Jones et al. 2016](#)), the corresponding datasets have frequently been used for
607 retrieving CDOM in oceanic and coastal waters ([Antoine, d'Ortenzio et al. 2008](#), [Brown, Huot et](#)

608 [al. 2008](#)).

609 **4.3. Turbidity or Total Suspended Matter/Solid (TSM/TSS)**

610 TSM or TSS is a sediment particle that is suspended and floated in the water column ([Manoppo](#)
611 [and Budhiman 2017](#)). Generally, TSM refers to all the extremely small suspended solids in water
612 that are not settled out by gravity ([Miller and McKee 2004](#), [Nechad, Ruddick et al. 2010](#)). These
613 solids include anything drifting or floating in the water, from sediment, silt, and sand to plankton
614 and algae. Since almost all solids present in the water are less clear than water, TSM is closely
615 related to the turbidity of water ([Dekker, Vos et al. 2001](#)). TSM, also known as turbidity, is one of
616 the key OWQ parameters, which has a significant impact on the migration of pollutants,
617 temperature, and marine life ([Moridnejad, Abdollahi et al. 2015](#)). The TSM concentrations also
618 play a key role in the clarity, turbidity, and color of the water column, especially in coastal waters
619 ([Kirk 1994](#), [Warrick 2002](#)).

620 According to the TSM retrieval theory, the RS signal is increased and decreased by the
621 backscattering and absorption properties of TSM, respectively. Thus, TSM can be estimated using
622 RS data ([Zhang, Tang et al. 2010](#)). Given the higher absorption of pure water in the NIR region
623 than in short visible bands, the NIR region and short visible bands are appropriate for estimating
624 the high TSM concentrations and low TSM, respectively ([Odermatt, Gitelson et al. 2012](#)).
625 Theoretically, the reflectance of a single band can provide a robust data for TSM estimation.
626 However, as mentioned before, it is difficult to assess TSM from the reflectance of a single band
627 because different types of complex substances in water simultaneously affect the spectral
628 properties of a water body. Therefore, similar to other OWQ parameters, TSM is usually retrieved
629 from the estimation of different spectral bands ([Nechad, Ruddick et al. 2010](#)). So far, several
630 empirical methods have been developed to retrieve TSM using various RS systems, some of which

631 are provided in [Table 4](#).

632 Table 4. Some of the most used empirical models for retrieving TSM using RS data.

Model	Reference
$TSM = -1.91 + 1140.25 \times R_{645}$	(Miller and McKee 2004)
$\log TSM = 9.0031 X + 0.9776$ $X = R_{840} / R_{545}$	(Doxaran, Froidefond et al. 2002)
$\log TSM = 2.5526 X + 1.2866$ $X = R_{840} / R_{645}$	(Doxaran, Froidefond et al. 2002)
$\log TSM = 12.474 X + 0.4256$ $X = [R_{550} + R_{670}] / [R_{550} / R_{670}]$	(Han, Jin et al. 2006)
$\log TSM = 2.4618 + 0.9905 \text{ Lg} (R_{555} + R_{645}) - 1.2073 \text{ Lg} (R_{488} / R_{555})$	(Tassan 1993)
$\log TSM = 0.6311 + 22.2158 \text{ Lg} (R_{555} + R_{645}) - 0.5239 (R_{488} / R_{555})$	(Zhang, Tang et al. 2010)

633 All the band combinations presented in [Table 4](#) are empirical methods and have been applied to
634 various optical satellite data. As mentioned in [Section 2](#), correlating the measured RS reflectance
635 data in various spectrum portions to OWQ parameters is a common empirical method to estimate
636 OWQ. To this end, the reflectance at different bands is determined and then, statistical
637 relationships (e.g., linear, polynomial, and logarithmic) between in-situ measurements and RS data
638 are generated. For example, [Tassan \(1993\)](#) used an empirical relationship to map the concentration
639 of TSM using Landsat TM data. Since TSM data retrieved from Landsat images with a revisit time
640 of 16 days couldn't capture the temporal dynamics of water, [Brown, Huot et al. \(2008\)](#) applied the
641 MODIS products with a daily temporal resolution to monitor near-real-time TSM. Later, [Zhang,](#)
642 [Tang et al. \(2010\)](#) showed that the model developed by [Tassan \(1993\)](#) couldn't meet the
643 requirements for the TSM retrieval in the Yellow and East China Seas. Thus, they developed a
644 new model using a novel atmospheric correction algorithm to retrieve TSM in the Yellow and East
645 China Seas from MODIS imagery. Moreover, [Miller and McKee \(2004\)](#) proposed an empirical

646 algorithm using Band 1 of MODIS/Terra and in-situ measurements of TSM. They reported that
647 the red band of MODIS (620–667 nm) was more appropriate in determining suspended particulates
648 in coastal waters due to medium spatial resolution, high sensitivity, and near-daily coverage
649 (Miller and McKee 2004). Another study conducted by Manoppo and Budhiman (2017) showed
650 that OLI/TIRS could be effectively used to retrieve TSM concentrations in coastal waters.
651 According to (El Din and Zhang 2017), the coastal blue, blue, green, and red bands of the OLI
652 have a high potential for modeling TSM concentrations. Choi, Park et al. (2014) also developed
653 an empirical algorithm to derive the TSM distribution from the GOCI satellite images over the
654 Mokpo coastal area. They also used a modified version of the Management Unit of the North Sea
655 Mathematical Models (MUMM) atmospheric correction algorithm to avoid the underestimation of
656 TSM values in areas with a high concentration. In this algorithm, the calibration parameter of
657 alpha, previously calculated using the reflectance values at 765 nm and 865 nm, was estimated
658 using an iterated calculation method. The comparison of the observed TSM maps with in-situ
659 measurements and MODIS-derived TSM concentration proved the high potential of the proposed
660 empirical TSM algorithm. Moreover, Brando and Dekker (2003) applied a Matrix Inversion
661 Method (MIM) to retrieve the concentrations of CDOM, Chl-a, and TSM from Hyperion imagery
662 in the complex waters of Moreton Bay. Through multiple iterations, two Hyperion bands centered
663 at 490 and 670 nm and the bin of five of the Hyperion bands in the 700–740 nm range were selected
664 to produce Chl-a, CDOM, and TSM maps. A sensitivity analysis on the retrieved concentrations
665 showed that the MIM-retrieved Hyperion-based maps could detect Chl-a, CDOM, and TSM at the
666 intervals of 2.32 $\mu\text{g/l}$, 0.06 m^{-1} , and 0.01 mg/l , respectively. Although empirical models have
667 proved to be practical to monitor TSM using RS data, semi-analytical methods are more efficient.
668 For example, the study conducted by Mao, Chen et al. (2012) showed the potential of the TSM

669 model improved by a combination of semi-analytical and empirical approaches. [Mao, Chen et al.](#)
670 [\(2012\)](#) also introduced a new model by a combination of an empirical and a semi-analytical
671 algorithm to estimate TSM concentration. To this end, four indices were constructed from a
672 combination of the reflectance data of various SeaWiFS bands to derive the complex proxy.
673 Additionally, [Manoppo and Budhiman \(2017\)](#) applied empirical and analytic approaches using the
674 bands 2, 3, and 4 of Landsat-8 OLI for estimating TSM in the Lombok coastal water. The values
675 of statistical indicators showed that the applied model had a better performance when Landsat
676 reflectance measurements were considered as the input values of the model (correlation coefficient
677 of 91% and RMSE of 0.52). In addition to single sensor-based algorithms, several studies took
678 advantage of the multiple sensor approaches. For example, [Nechad, Ruddick et al. \(2010\)](#)
679 developed a multi sensor model to retrieve TSM concentration in turbid water. They used
680 hyperspectral calibration to identify the best spectral interval for TSM retrieval from reflectance
681 data collected by MERIS, MODIS, and SeaWiFS.

682 **4.4. Dissolved Organic Carbon (DOC)**

683 Besides CDOM, any organic matter that can pass through a filter is referred to as DOM. DOM
684 plays a critical role in the aquatic ecosystem ([Hartnett 2017](#)). DOM has three components: DOC,
685 Dissolved Organic Nitrogen (DON), and Dissolved Organic Phosphorous (DOP) ([Kobayashi,](#)
686 [Nakada et al. 2017](#)). Among these components, DOC has the most considerable effect on the
687 carbon cycle ([Hansell and Carlson 1998](#)). In the open ocean, there are low and uniform DOC
688 concentrations. However, there are high DOC concentrations and a large DOC variation in the
689 coastal ocean ([Liu, Pan et al. 2014](#)). Therefore, researchers usually only focus on DOC to study
690 DOM in coastal waters, bays, and shallow seas. DOC, which represents most of the organic
691 material in most water samples, refers to the total quantity of organic carbon compounds that pass

692 through a 0.45 μm filter. DOC is considered as one of the chemical characteristics of water that
693 affects a range of geochemical processes by directly controlling pH levels. DOC directly and
694 indirectly affects aquatic habitats and human health and, therefore, is one of the most important
695 parameters of OWQ, especially in coastal regions.

696 DOC concentration cannot directly be measured from OC sensors (López, Del Castillo et al. 2012).
697 Many studies have shown that DOC is strongly correlated with CDOM and, thus, CDOM is
698 commonly used as a proxy for DOC concentration (Ferrari 2000, Del Vecchio and Blough 2004,
699 Guéguen, Guo et al. 2005, Fichot and Benner 2012). For instance, Ferrari, Dowell et al. (1996)
700 observed a strong correlation coefficient up to 0.9 between DOC and the aCDOM at 335 nm in the
701 southern Baltic Sea. Furthermore, Rochelle-Newall and Fisher (2002) found a significant
702 relationship between aCDOM at 335 nm and DOC ($p < 0.01$, $R^2 = 0.59$) in Chesapeake Bay.
703 Consequently, DOC concentration can be estimated based on the empirical relationship between
704 DOC and the satellite-derived CDOM in the ocean (Swan, Siegel et al. 2009, Matsuoka, Hooker
705 et al. 2013) and coastal water (Liu, Pan et al. 2013). As an example, Figure 6 shows the three-year
706 mean value of DOC extracted from the CDOM products of MODIS with the spatial resolution of
707 9 km using a Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) algorithm (Aurin, Mannino et al. 2018).

708

709 Figure 6. The three-year mean value of Dissolved Organic Carbon (DOC) retrieved from MODIS data with the
 710 spatial resolution of 9 km using an MLR algorithm and Colored Dissolve Organic Matter (CDOM) (Aurin, Mannino
 711 et al. 2018).

712 Regarding RS systems, the hourly GOCI images with a spatial resolution of 500 m have a high
 713 potential for investigating DOC in coastal water. Moreover, SeaWiFS and MODIS images have
 714 widely been used for mapping CDOM and DOC concentrations in the U.S. Middle Atlantic Bight
 715 (Mannino, Russ et al. 2008). For example, Mannino, Russ et al. (2008) applied an empirical least-
 716 squares approach to estimate DOC from aCDOM using SeaWiFS and MODIS data in the U.S.
 717 Middle Atlantic Bight. The percentage of the mean absolute differences was less than 0.9% for
 718 DOC estimation, indicating the high accuracy of their proposed method. Furthermore, Liu, Pan et
 719 al. (2014) monitored DOC in the East China Sea using the integration of the surface DOC with
 720 two vertical models of the DOC profile generated from MODIS satellite data. Liu, Pan et al. (2014)
 721 also estimated surface DOC concentration from the satellite-derived CDOM and Chl-a. To this

722 end, two vertical DOC profile models were established based on water-density profiles and were
723 applied to water mass classification. Finally, Cao, Tzortziou et al. (2018) developed an empirical
724 algorithm for the DOC estimation using MERIS and MODIS data in different coastal environments
725 (i.e., the northern Gulf of Mexico, the Delaware Bay, the Chesapeake Bay estuary, and the Middle
726 Atlantic Bight coastal waters). The CDOM absorption and its spectral slope (275–295 nm) were
727 retrieved using MLR and linear and non-linear band-ratio approaches. Afterwards, DOC
728 concentrations were obtained from a relationship between the CDOM absorption (at both 300 nm
729 and 355 nm) and slope (275ⁱ–295 nm). The percentage of the mean absolute differences were 18%
730 and 33% for DOC retrieval using MERIS and MODIS data, respectively.

731 **4.5. Secchi Disk Depth (SDD)**

732 SSD (Z_{SD}), also known as water clarity, is defined as a measure of the transparency of the water.
733 In another word, SSD refers to the depth of water, from which the Secchi disk is not visible. Figure
734 7 shows the location of the in-situ stations of the global SDD research, whose data is available at
735 <https://www.playingwithdata.com/secchi-disk-project/>. As can be seen, despite the dense stations
736 around the coastal area, these data are not updated due to the limitation of SSD or water clarity
737 monitoring from ground stations or ship surveys. To overcome this issue, RS satellite technology
738 has extensively been used for measuring large-scale and long-term water clarity (Liu, Xiao et al.
739 2020).

740

741 Figure 7. The global study of the Secchi disk along with the information and the measurements of one random

742 station (<https://www.playingwithdata.com/secchi-disk-project/>).

743 Based on the classical underwater visibility theory, Z_{SD} is defined as an inverse function of the

744 beam attenuation coefficient and the diffuse attenuation coefficient (K_d) of downwelling irradiance

745 (Duntley and Preisendorfer 1952, Preisendorfer 1986). Considering the observations of the human

746 eye in the model, a new model for Z_{SD} has been established, which is inversely proportional to the

747 diffuse attenuation coefficient at a wavelength corresponding to the maximum transparency for

748 such interpretations (Lee, Shang et al. 2015). Therefore, satellite-derived K_d can be used for
749 estimating Z_{SD} . In this regard, empirical algorithms have widely been applied to determine K_d and
750 Z_{SD} (Chen, Muller-Karger et al. 2007). For example, the empirical method introduced by Mueller
751 (2000) derived K_d based on a ratio band of the reflectance values at 490 and 555 nm. Moreover,
752 another empirical method proposed by Morel (1988) estimated a strong relationship between Chl-
753 a and K_d . It should be noted that these two algorithms were designed for the case-1 water and were
754 not appropriate for the case-2 water.

755 Many studies have shown that SDD can be estimated using visual spectral bands and various band
756 ratios. For instance, Ekercin (2007) presented an algorithm using bands 1, 2, and 3 of the high-
757 resolution IKONOS data for monitoring SDD, Chl-a, and TSS concentration, with a correlation
758 coefficient of more than 0.97 for SSD estimation. Besides the empirical algorithms, semi-
759 analytical algorithms have been used to retrieve Z_{SD} in different water bodies (Doron, Babin et al.
760 2011, Liu, Xiao et al. 2020). For example, in the semi-analytical method proposed by Lee, Darecki
761 et al. (2005), the relationship between the total absorption, backscattering of optically active
762 constituents, solar zenith angle, and K_d were employed to estimate SSD. Furthermore, QAA
763 introduced by Lee, Carder et al. (2002) was applied to retrieve Z_{SD} using multi-source RS data
764 (e.g., Terra MODIS and Landsat-8 OLI images). They reported that their proposed method had a
765 high capability to estimate SSD in a wide range of Z_{SD} values compared to in-situ measurements
766 from various water bodies. Additionally, Al Kaabi, Zhao et al. (2016) evaluated two empirical and
767 one semi-analytical methods to estimate SDD using MODIS/Aqua over the Arabian Gulf. Finally,
768 Doron, Babin et al. (2011) compared the performance of an empirical and two semi-analytical
769 algorithms using MERIS, MODIS, and SeaWiFS data in both coastal and oceanic waters. The
770 proposed empirical algorithm related ocean reflectance at wavelengths of 490 and 590 nm and

771 SSD. Due to the less sensitivity to the error caused by erroneous atmospheric correction, the
772 empirical method provided better results. ML algorithms have also a great potential for predicting
773 SSD values of oceans. For instance, [KS, RL et al. \(1998\)](#) developed an ANN algorithm to estimate
774 SSD using a combination of water-leaving radiance ratios and SeaWiFS bands. [Zhang, Pulliainen
775 et al. \(2003\)](#) also used MLR and ANN for determining the SDD over the Gulf of Finland and the
776 Archipelago Sea. In this study, Landsat/TM and European Remote Sensing satellite-2 (ERS-2)
777 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data were employed. The results indicated that the accuracy of
778 ANN was higher than other methods. It was also concluded that SAR images improved the SDD
779 estimation.

780 **4.6. Suspended Sediment Concentration (SSC)**

781 SSC is one of the key OWQ parameters, which has significant impacts on pollutants, SST, and
782 marine life ([Moridnejad, Abdollahi et al. 2015](#)). Generally, when the water is not moving, mineral
783 and organic matter fall to the stream bed to become bottom sediment ([Skolasińska and Nowak
784 2018, Seenipandi, Ramachandran et al. 2021](#)). As such, deposited sediment is often mineral-rich
785 and makes excellent farmland. However, where water moves faster further downstream, the
786 sediment may build up on the bottom or it may be picked and create SSC. As a result, similar to
787 the TSS, the SSC is strongly related to turbidity. Studying the SSC in the open ocean makes no
788 sense because the SSC is naturally a phenomenon that occurs in shallow water. On the other hand,
789 although the absorption in coastal ocean water is mainly controlled by Chl-a, CDOM, and
790 particulate matter, most of the scattering in the shallow coastal water is caused by SSC.

791 SSC can be estimated through single band or ratio empirical algorithms ([Baruah, Tamura et al.
792 2001](#)). According to the literature, the red and NIR bands have a great potential for estimating SSC
793 concentrations in OW ([Bhatti, Rundquist et al. 2008](#)). Based on this theory, [Bhatti, Rundquist et](#)

794 [al. \(2008\)](#) developed a multiplicative model using the NIR and red bands, which showed promising
795 results in estimating suspended sediments. In case-2 water, the interaction between RS data and
796 OWQ parameters, including Chl-a and turbidity, can be modeled by non-linear equations. In this
797 regard, the models, which are based on LR and PCA, may fail in estimating SSC ([Lathrop 1992](#)).
798 In such cases, ML algorithms have widely been utilized ([Keiner and Yan 1998](#), [Tanaka, Kishino](#)
799 [et al. 2000](#), [Wang, Zhou et al. 2009](#)). For example, [Keiner and Yan \(1998\)](#) applied an ANN
800 algorithm to estimate SSC using Landsat/TM visible bands. A similar study was carried out by
801 [Tanaka, Kishino et al. \(2000\)](#) to examine an ANN algorithm for retrieving turbidity and SSC using
802 Ocean Color and Temperature Scanner (OCTS) data in the Yellow Sea. They evaluated three
803 different algorithms, including a standard algorithm for OCTS (i.e., SSC retrieval from the
804 normalized water-leaving radiance using 670 and 865 nm domains for the atmospheric correction
805 bands), an ANN model in-water algorithm using 765 and 865 nm for the atmospheric correction
806 bands, and an ANN algorithm as an atmosphere-ocean coupled algorithm using all bands, which
807 showed reasonable results of turbidity concentration. [Zhang, Pulliainen et al. \(2002\)](#) also presented
808 an empirical ANN algorithm to estimate OWQ parameters, such as SSC, using a combination of
809 optical (Landsat) and MW (ERS-2) datasets in the Gulf of Finland. The results indicated that ANN
810 outperformed regression analysis in almost all cases of waters. It was also proved that MW data
811 could improve the accuracy of the model.

812 **4.7. Sea Surface Temperature (SST)**

813 SST is defined as the skin temperature close to the ocean's surface. SST is a vital quantity in the
814 process of ocean systems by contributing to the exchange of heat, water, gas, and momentum
815 between the atmosphere and the ocean ([Shutler, Quartly et al. 2016](#)). SST data is mostly derived
816 from satellite observations using either the TIR or passive MW sensors ([Azevedo, Rudorff et al.](#)

817 [2021](#)). For instance, the NOAA’s next-generation geostationary environmental satellites (GOES-
818 16) satellite provides timely and high-quality SST data along other met-ocean products. Although
819 TIR sensors are capable to obtain a relatively high spatial resolution, their application is limited to
820 non-cloudy or foggy regions ([Amani, Mahdavi et al. 2020](#), [Mahdavi, Amani et al. 2020](#), [Azevedo,
821 Rudorff et al. 2021](#)). Conversely, MW sensors, such as the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission
822 (TRMM), Microwave Imager (TMI), the WindSat onboard Coriolis, and the Advanced Microwave
823 Scanning Radiometer for Earth Observation System (AMSR-E), can measure SST under cloudy
824 regions. However, SST products generated by MW systems usually contain missing data due to
825 low spatial resolution, especially near coastlines ([Carr, Lamont et al. 2021](#)). To overcome the
826 drawbacks of TIR and MW sensors, several studies have utilized a combination of these datasets
827 to measure SST with a high spatial resolution, high accuracy, and full spatiotemporal coverage
828 ([Guan and Kawamura 2004](#)). For instance, [Cao, Mao et al. \(2021\)](#) applied multi-source RS data,
829 including those recorded by two TIR (MODIS and AVHRR) and three MW (AMSR-E, AMSR2,
830 WindSat) radiometers, to generate a unified global SST product between 2002–2019. It was proved
831 that the new reconstructed SST product was reliable for regional and global SST studies.

832 Many approaches have so far been investigated to predict SST based on empirical regression
833 analysis ([McClain, Pichel et al. 1985](#), [Walton, Pichel et al. 1998](#), [Kilpatrick, Podesta et al. 2001](#))
834 and ML methods ([Sunder, Ramsankaran et al. 2020](#)). Over the past two decades, Neural Network
835 (NN)-based algorithms, such as Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) ([Ali, Swain et al. 2004](#)), ANN
836 ([Gupta and Malmgren 2009](#), [Patil and Deo 2017](#)), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Back
837 Propagation Neural Network (BPNN), and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), have
838 extensively been used to predict SST (see [Table 5](#) for some examples). The timeline of the
839 applications of various NN-based models for SST prediction is also shown in [Figure 8](#). As is clear,

840 the LSTM and CNN algorithms have recently attracted significant attention for predicting SST.

841 Table 5. Examples of ML models for SST estimation (AdaBoost: Adaptive Boosting, XGBoost: Extreme Gradient
842 Boosting, GED: GRU Encoder-Decoder).

Models	Satellite data	Best Model	Study Area	Reference
SVR, LSTM, convolutional LSTM	AVHRR	convolutional LSTM	China Sea	(Xiao, Chen et al. 2019)
LSTM-AdaBoost, SVR, BPNN, LSTM	AVHRR	LSTM-AdaBoost	China Sea	(Xiao, Chen et al. 2019)
LSTM, SVR, GED	NOAA/OISST	LSTM	Bohai Sea and South China Sea.	(Xie, Zhang et al. 2019)
LSTM, GAM, RF, MLP, XGBoost,	MODIS	LSTM	North Atlantic	(Wolff, O'Donncha et al. 2020)

843

844

845 Figure 8. The timeline of the applications of various Neural Network (NN)-based models for Sea Surface
846 Temperature (SST) estimation (Hagbhin, Sharafati et al. 2021)

847 Additionally, several studies have compared different NN algorithms for SST estimation. In this
848 regard, many studies have demonstrated the capabilities of the LSTM model for estimating SST
849 (Yang, Dong et al. 2017, Liu, Zhang et al. 2018, Xiao, Chen et al. 2019, Xiao, Chen et al. 2019).

850 For example, [Xiao, Chen et al. \(2019\)](#) compared LSTM, convolutional LSTM, and SVR to
851 estimate SST in the East China Sea using NOAA/OISST data. It was concluded that the
852 convolutional LSTM model provided the best prediction performance. However, [Barth, Alvera](#)
853 [Azcárate et al. \(2020\)](#) argued that the CNN model was superior.

854 **5. Conclusion**

855 Monitoring OWQ is necessary due to the undeniable impacts of water on human life and ecosystem
856 health. RS techniques in conjunction with in-situ measurements are very beneficial for monitoring
857 OWQ parameters in both the open ocean (case-1 waters) and coastal regions (case-2 waters). The
858 main idea behind RS techniques in OWQ studies is that almost all WQ parameters are optically
859 measurable components and can be quantitatively derived using satellite data. In case-1 water,
860 these parameters include. In case-2 waters, are included. This study provided a review of the OWQ
861 parameters (e.g., Chl-a, CDOM, SDD, turbidity, TSS, SST, and COD) and the corresponding
862 monitoring models using various RS datasets.

863 Among the RS techniques applied to assess OWQ (e.g., empirical, semi-empirical, semi-analytical,
864 and analytical methods), semi-analytical models combined with multivariate statistical analysis
865 approaches have received considerable attention from researchers. However, analytical
866 approaches are less applicable to retrieve OWQ parameters due to their complexity in terms of
867 their theory and implementation. Although empirical and semi-empirical models, which are mostly
868 based on ratios or differences of spectral reflectance in the blue, green, and NIR domains of the
869 electromagnetic spectrum, are easy to implement, they have multiple limitations. For example,
870 they need enough in-situ measurements to estimate the algorithm coefficients. To circumvent this
871 constraint, the integration of RS datasets with products derived from alternative environmental and
872 empirical models have been employed. For example, it can be investigated whether using various

873 databases captured at the same time allows for the monitoring and mapping of OWQ
874 characteristics without the need for auxiliary in-situ data. It can also be evaluated whether a given
875 OWQ parameter can be predicted using real-time estimation of another water parameter.
876 Nevertheless, the review demonstrates that there are many studies that used empirical and semi-
877 empirical models for OWQ monitoring.

878 In terms of RS systems, passive sensors have extensively been employed for OWQ assessment.
879 Among the various spectral domains of RS systems, the optical and TIR domains of the
880 electromagnetic spectrum (e.g., the spectral bands of MSS, TM, ETM+, OLI, MODIS, and
881 SeaWiFS) have mostly been utilized in OWQ studies. MODIS and SeaWiFS have frequently been
882 used for retrieving OWQ parameters in oceanic and coastal waters. Additionally, passive MW
883 sensors, such as TMI, WindSat, and AMSR2, provide accurate measurements of SST.

884 We expect that this review of monitoring OWQ parameters can promote the development of
885 corresponding theories and techniques. Future studies can use this review paper to better
886 understand the effects of various OWQ parameters on the spectral characteristics of water and
887 discover which one of the OWQ parameters is more important given various cases of water and
888 different characteristics of their study area. Moreover, this study comprehensively represented all
889 the RS techniques and instruments applied for OWQ retrieval and described the main benefits and
890 limitations of each. Therefore, future researchers can choose the most appropriate method and data
891 to determine open ocean or coastal WQ, based on available in-situ data, cost, and geographical
892 characteristics of the study area.

893 **Appendix A**

894 Table A. Acronyms and corresponding descriptions

Acronym	Description	Acronym	Description
ABI	Advanced Baseline Imager	MSI	MultiSpectral Instrument
aCDOM	absorption coefficient of CDOM	MUMM	Management Unit of the North Sea Mathematical Models
AHI	Advanced Himawari Imager	MW	passive Microwave
AMSR-E	Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer for Earth Observation System	NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
ANN	Artificial Neural Network	NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
AOPs	Apparent Optical Properties	NFLH	Normalized Fluorescence Line Height
ASTER	Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer	NIR	Near Infrared
AVHRR-3	Advanced Very High-Resolution Radiometer	NN	Neural Network
BOD	Biochemical Oxygen Demand	NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
BPNN	Back Propagation Neural Network	NOMAD	NASA bio-Optical Marine Algorithm Data set
CA	Cluster Analysis	NWQD	National Water Quality Data
CDOM	Colored Dissolved Organic Matter	OC	Ocean Color
Chl-a	Chlorophyll-a	OCR	Ocean Color Radiometry
CIA	Color Index Algorithm	OCRS	Ocean Color Remote Sensing
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks	OCTS	Ocean Color and Temperature Scanner
COD	Chemical Oxygen Demand	OLCI	Ocean and Land Colour Instrument
DA	Discriminant Analysis	OLI	Operational Land Imager
DNN	Deep Neural Network	ONNS	OLCI Neural Network Swarm
DO	Dissolved Oxygen	OSA	Optical Sensor Assembly
DOC	Dissolved Organic Carbon	OWQ	Ocean Water Quality
DON	Dissolved Organic Nitrogen	OW	Ocean Water
DOP	Dissolved Organic Phosphorous	OWT	Optical Water Type
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency	PAR	Photo synthetically Active Radiation
ERS-2	European Remote Sensing satellite-2	PCA	Component Analysis
ETM+	Thematic Mapper Plus	PIC	Particulate Inorganic Carbon
FA	Factor Analysis	POC	Particulate Organic Carbon
FAI	Floating Algae Index	QAA	Quasi Analytical Algorithm
FDA	Food and Drug Administration	RF	Random Forest
FLH	Fluorescence Line Height	RLR	Regularized Linear Regression
GEE	Google Earth Engine	RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
GIS-MS	GIS-Multispectral	RS	Remote Sensing
GOCI	Geostationary Ocean Colour Imager	RT	Radiative Transfer
GPR	Gaussian Process Regression	SAI	Scaled Algae Index
GSM	Garver–Siegel–Maritorena	SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
HICO	Hyperspectral Imager for the Coastal Ocean	SDD	Secchi Disk Depth
HRG	High Resistance Grounding	SeaWiFS	Sea-Viewing Wide Field-of-View Sensor

IDW	Inverse Distance Weighted	SGLI	Second Generation GLObal Imager
IOPs	Inherent Optical Properties	SMAP	Soil Moisture Active Passive
JAXA	Japan Aerospace eXploration Agency	SMOS	Soil Moisture Ocean Salinity
KNN	K-nearest Neighbors	SSC	Suspended Sediment Concentration
KRR	Kernel Ridge Regression	SSS	Sea Surface Salinity
LMM	Linear Matrix Model	SST	Sea Surface Temperature
LR	Linear Regression	SVM	Support Vector Machine
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory	SWIR	Short-Wave Infrared
MAPE	Mean Absolute Percentage Error	TAC	Thematic Assembly Centra
MCI	Maximum Chlorophyll Index	TIR	Thermal InfraRed
MERIS	MEdium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer	TMI	TRMM Microwave Imager
MIM	Matrix Inversion Method	TP	Total Phosphorus
ML	Machine Learning	TRMM	Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron	TSS	Total Suspended Solids
MLR	Multiple Linear Regression	US	United States
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer	WHO	World Health Organization
MRE	Mean Relative Error	WQ	Water Quality

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